

Interview Guide

Table 1: Interview guideline for the semi-structured interview (Part 1).

Part	Section	Questions and Explanation
1	Informed Consent	<i>Written and orally.</i>
2	Introduction and Agenda	<p>Thank you for your participation in our interview study about what happens when someone steals your phone. We will start with some general questions regarding stolen smartphones and privacy. Then, we will ask you to describe the incident that led to your phone being stolen. Towards the end of the interview, we will ask you some questions based on some commonly used apps on phones.</p> <p>Before we proceed, please remember that there are no right or wrong answers and we ask you to say anything that comes to your mind. You also don't have to answer any questions that you don't want to.</p> <p>Are you OK to continue? Do you consent to recording this interview?</p>
3	Warm-Up Phase	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How long have you been using a smartphone? 2. What do you generally use your smartphone for? 3. Have you ever lost a smartphone? <p>Follow-up: Was it stolen, or did you simply misplace it?</p> <p><i>Make the participants feel comfortable with the interview and try to slowly bring in the main topic.</i></p>
4	Preparation	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What do you think happens when somebody steals your phone? 2. What is the worst thing that you can think of if your smartphone is stolen? Follow-up: Why did you come up with these things? Follow-up #2: What about your privacy? <i>Follow-up #2 only used, if participants did not bring up privacy in the first question.</i> 3. What steps do you take such that no one can access your smartphone? Follow-up: In case your smartphone gets stolen, how do you make sure that no one other than you can access it? 4. Can you think of ways (e.g., settings on your phone) which make it difficult for people other than you to gain access to your smartphone?
5	Content Warning and Incident Description	<p>CONTENT WARNING: Next I would like to ask you to describe the incident that led to you having your device stolen.</p> <p>I understand that this may be hard for you and bring back unpleasant memories. At this point, I would like to reiterate that you can pause this interview or skip questions at any time without reason. You can also tell us if you are uncomfortable sharing any details.</p> <p>Are you OK to continue?</p>

Table 2: Interview guideline for the semi-structured interview (Part 2).

Part	Section	Questions and Explanation
6	Theft Phase	<p>1. Can you describe the incident which led to you losing your smartphone? <i>Follow-up:</i> How did you feel when that happened?</p> <p>2. What was your first concern after losing your smartphone?</p> <p>3. Can you remember if your smartphone was locked or unlocked?</p> <p>4. Who do you think could have access to your data? <i>Ask about 2FA, freezing bank cards and SIM card, Apple/Google Pay, backup behavior, Apple/Google account passwords, and password managers.</i></p> <p>5. At the time, were you aware of any settings on your phone that made it difficult for people other than you to gain access to your smartphone? <i>Follow-up:</i> Can you remember if any of these settings were enabled on your smartphone?</p> <p>6. Can you walk us through the first things you did upon losing your smartphone?</p> <p>7. How and why did you decide what to do these things first?</p> <p>8. Did you seek any advice or help? Why/why not? <i>Follow-up:</i> Who or where did you seek advice from?</p> <p>9. How helpful was the advice you received?</p>
7	Post-Theft Phase	<p>1. What actually happened after the incident? (Financial loss, data loss, identity theft?)</p> <p>2. Did you regain access to your smartphone?</p> <p>3. Have you changed the way you use your smartphone after this incident?</p> <p>4. What additional precautions do you take to avoid such an incident?</p> <p>5. Can you describe your experience trying to recover all the apps you had on your previous device? <i>Only ask, if participants said that they were not able to recover their device and bought a new one.</i> <i>Follow-up:</i> Did you face any difficulties?</p> <p>6. Were you able to re-login to your old apps easily? <i>Follow-up:</i> Did you remember your passwords to re-login to the apps?</p>
8	Harms and Most Critical Apps	<p>Having your phone stolen can cause different kind of harms. We have categorized them into 5 dimensions. I will now show them to you by sharing my screen.</p> <p>1. If you think about your incident, what kind of economic harm did you have to go through? <i>Now, let's consider the hypothetical situation that the attacker has your PIN.</i></p> <p>2. Can you point to specific applications on your phone which in your opinion can cause these harms? <i>Follow-up:</i> Repeat for each harm.</p>
9	Cooldown Phase	<p>Have you heard about what phone companies are doing to protect people in case they lose their phone? <i>Talk about Stolen Device Protection on iOS and Private Space on Android.</i></p>